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STUDY OF CONSUMER LOYALTY TOWARDS PRIVATE LABELS IN BANGALORE (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO FOOD & GROCERY)

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ABSTRACT

The increase of private labels in food retailing and retailers' high expenditures for establishing their store brands or private labels raise one central question: Do consumers really consider private labels as real brands and develop "loyalty" towards them? In recent time's, Bangalore has witnessed growth in sales and development of private labels, but does this fact also support the aspect of Consumer Loyalty towards Private Labels, specifically in the Food & Grocery Departments. Intense competition in the market has forced retailers to rethink their strategies to compete with company brands. Now, it becomes vital for the retailers to look out for new avenues and opportunities to make their customers happy. This aspect leads to analyse the fact as to how sensitive are customers towards product quality, brand choice and sales promotion activities undertaken by retailers for the sale and acceptance of private labels. This paper seeks to analyses the level of acceptance of private labels and their loyalty towards the same at large. This analysis thus proves that private labels are being successful in positioning themselves significantly in the minds of the customers and are gaining acceptance. With acceptance come's belief, preference and loyalty.

KEYWORDS: Food Retail, Private Labels, Store Brands, Customer Loyalty, Product Acceptance.

INTRODUCTION

Retailing has been the most active and attractive sector of the last decade. While retailing industry itself has been present from time unknown, it is only the recent past that has paved way for much of the dynamism. 'Indian retailing' today is at an interesting crossroads. The urban retail market has been embracing various new formats and the malls are turning out to be the trend setters by promising the concept of 'shoppertainment'.

The practices of the rural market has also been changing from the old Haats and Mela's to rural malls like 'Chaupal Sagar' launched by ITC, 'Hariyali Bazaar' a one-stop shopping destination set up DCM Sriram Groups, 'Adhar' an agri-store launched by Godrej Groups, etc. The whole concept of shopping has been altered in terms of format and consumer buying behavior, making way for a revolution in concept of shopping in India. Modern retail, as seen in India as sprawling

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shopping centers, multi-storied malls and huge complexes offer shopping, entertainment and food all under one roof. Retail Space is no more a constraint for growth, as global retailers and brands worldwide are willing to partner with Indian retailers like Tata, Reliance, Raheja, ITC, Bombay Dyeing, Murugappa & Piramal Groups etc.

RETAIL FORMATS IN INDIA¹

- ◆ Hyper markets / super markets : Big Bazaar, Hyper City
- ◆ Department stores / convenience store: Landmark Group, Lifestyle.
- ◆ Specialty Stores: Crossword, Music World
- ◆ Discount Stores : Piramal's TruMart
- ◆ Category Killers: Multi Brand Outlet's Like Brand Factory, Metro.
- ◆ Kirana Stores

PRESENT INDIAN SCENARIO

- * Unorganized market: Rs. 583,000 crores
- * Organized market: Rs.5, 000 crores
- * 5X growth in organized retailing between 2000-2005
- * Over 4,000 new modern Outlets in the last 3 years
- * Over 5,000,000 sq. ft. of mall space under development
- * The top 3 modern retailers control over 750,000 sq. ft. of retail space
- * Over 400,000 shoppers walk through their doors every week

Customer Loyalty is feelings or attitudes that incline a customer either to return to a company, shop or outlet to purchase there again or else to re-purchase a particular product, service or brand.

Oliver's Loyalty Phases: Consumers are theorized to become loyal in a cognitive sense first, then later in an affective sense, still later in a co native manner, and finally in a behavioral manner, which is described as "action inertia."

Cognitive loyalty is the first loyalty phase and is based on brand belief only, i.e. prior or knowledge or on recent experience-based information.

Affective loyalty at the second phase of loyalty, develops a liking or attitude toward the brand which has developed on the basis of cumulatively satisfying usage occasions.

Co native loyalty at the third phase of loyalty is at a behavioral intention and is influenced by repeated episodes of positive affect of usage towards the brand.

Action loyalty is a mechanism that converts an intension into action, i.e. readiness to re-purchase.

Private Labels, also called store brands, are products that are developed by a retailer, are available for sale only through that retailer and are owned by the retailer themselves. In India, private labels presently contribute a turnover of approximately Rs.700 crore. Various retail entities have launched private label in the recent past and most of them have been either from the food or apparel industry. However in India, people's awareness regarding store brands is slow and hence when it comes to acceptance, they shy away from store brands and preferred to stick with the tried and tasted national brand. The prominent aspect for the organized retailer to do is to educate the customers and understand their buying behavior, in order to make inroads into their perceptual territory.

Over the years, private labels have been found to offer customers not just cheaper alternatives, but also quality products. Quality products at competitive prices have made customers to adopt private labels both globally and in India. It is being observed that as the retail market matures and expands across the country, private labels will constitute a bigger part of organized retail in the country. It has happened in a major way in the US and Europe more than a decade before. A successful private label can strengthen the negotiating position of retailers in relation to national brand.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dhar and Stephen (1997) a study conducted on store brand penetration revealed that the introduction of private labels by the retailers will change the status of the retailer from a consumer to a competitor. The findings highlighted that strategic decisions such as development, sourcing, warehousing and merchandising is to be taken care by the retailers. Other findings such as the breadth of private labels, commitment to quality, number of stores and use of the own name or store name will help in enhancing the performance of the store brands across the product categories. In lower quality categories, every Day Low Prices is beneficial. The paper also mentions that a proper balance needs to be maintained between both national and store brands, as national brands with their deeper assortment pull's the crowd. Whenever a price differential is observed between a national brand and store brand product category, then private labels exert a positive influence on the store performance. When category sales are good, it is observed by the retailers that the store brands in those categories perform better. In case of high quality

store brand, variance between the store brand and the national brand can be reduced by the practice adopted by the retailers.

Serdar Sayman (2002) this study has found that popular national brands are usually targeted by premium quality store brands. They also observed that competition is more intense, when high quality store brands. They also observed that competition is more intense, when high quality store brands compete with leading national brands and then secondary national brands. Product perception study objective highlighted, that when customers were targeted explicitly, consumers were influenced by physical product similarity and not by product quality similarity.

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2A. RESEARCH GAP

Previous research's have focused predominantly on promotional aspects of Store Brands alone and have not given much importance in focusing the requirements of the customers in purchasing and continuous usage of Private labels, unlike the Company brands which focus on retaining customers and modifies products and services based on the customers choice in order to draw their interest and retain the same, paving way for loyalty. As the study is restricted to the geographic location of Bangalore, with special reference to food and grocery and in perspective of customer loyalty, they are subject to certain limitations.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3A. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Analysis of a customer's loyalty towards Private labels or Store brands in comparison with company brands and how sensitive are customer's product quality, brand choice and sales promotion activities undertaken by retailers for the sale and acceptance of private labels.

3B. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- ↳ To study the factors driving the customer to the stores.
- ↳ To study the association between private labels quality and customer loyalty
- ↳ To study the influence of price differential between company brand and private label on customer loyalty.
- ↳ To know the impact of private label's promotion on customer loyalty.
- ↳ To study the influence of store name as private label name on customer loyalty.

3C. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study is an attempt to understand the loyalty of consumers towards Private Labels or Store Brands. It attempts to analyse, 'how aware are the consumer's about the private labels and does their consumption patterns get affected by these private labels'?

This study would be useful for retailers to understand a consumer's needs and buying patterns with regards to Store Brands. The study has been conducted in Bangalore, where the focus is given to those consumers who purchase and consume private labels on the go.

3D. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- * **Population:** People in Bangalore who consume Private Labels.
- * **Type of Research:** Exploratory type.
- * **Sampling Technique:** Convenience Sampling
- * **Sample Size:** 100 respondents in the age group of 20-55 years.
- * **Data Collection Instrument:** Questionnaire

AREA OF ENQUIRY AND SAMPLE

Customer's who use & consume private labels (Food and Grocery Category) in Bangalore, in the age group of 20-55 years.

The research investigation was a specific sample and limited to a sample size of 100. The sample size is based on exploratory study.

4. DATA COLLECTION

A) Primary Data

The primary data was collected through direct observation of customers and personal interaction through means of a questionnaire.

Pilot survey: Initially a pilot survey was undertaken to collect information regarding various private label products (related to food and grocery). This data was then used to identify the problem statement for this particular analysis, followed by setting of objectives & to prepare an appropriate questionnaire.

Survey: The questionnaire was personally filled in by the respondents. The questions asked were predominantly close-ended, multiple choice and Rating oriented questions.

B) SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data has been gathered from journals, Business magazines, research papers and Internet sources.

5. TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

Chi-Square Test is used to test the relationship between two variables such as Store Loyalty and Quality of Private Labels.

HYPOTHESIS 1:

H_0 : Null Hypothesis: Store loyalty and quality of private labels are independent of each other.

H_A : Alternate Hypothesis: Store loyalty and quality of private labels are dependent on each other.

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Visit the same retail mall for main grocery shopping	32*5=160	48*4=192	12*3=36	4*2=8	4*1=4	400
Usually use the same retail mall but occasionally use the other	0	100*4=400	0	0	0	400
Don't really have a regular retail mall and tend to use whichever is convenient	12*5=60	40*4=160	20*3=60	24*2=48	4*1=4	332
Generally rely on Kirana Stores and use retail mall occasionally	24*5=120	36*4=144	8*3=24	24*2=48	8*1=8	344
Grand Total						1476

Calculated Value of χ^2 (10.6123) was more than the tabulated value of χ^2 (7.814), thereby rejecting the null hypothesis and stating that Store Loyalty and quality of private labels are dependent on each other.

HYPOTHESIS 2:

H_0 : Null Hypothesis: There is independent relationship between private label's promotion and customer loyalty.

H_b : Alternate Hypothesis: There is dependent relationship between private label's promotion and customer loyalty.

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Helps deciding which malls offers competitive deal	20*5=100	40*4=160	32*3=96	4*2=8	4*1=4	368
Make it difficult to compare different supermarkets	56*5=280	0	28*3=84	16*2=32	0	396
Helps in trying new products	16*5=80	56*4=224	24*3=72	4*2=8	0	384
Don't really affect my choice	12*5=60	12*4=48	36*3=108	40*2=80	0	296
Grand Total						1444

Calculated Value of χ^2 (16.6981) was more than the tabulated value of χ^2 (7.814), thereby rejecting the null hypothesis and stating that there is a dependent relationship between private label's promotion and customer loyalty.

6. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

- ✧ Time constraint is one of the major limitations, as the study requires longer period of time.
- ✧ Resource constraints
- ✧ Limited to distribution channel in Bangalore only. Whole Indian market is not considered.
- ✧ There was no way to check consumer bias in providing information through the questionnaire or through personal observation. The generalization of results therefore had to be done very carefully.

7. RESEARCH FINDINGS

- ☆ Most of the customers visit the retail mall once in a month.
- ☆ Most of the customers prefer to shop from retail malls for their food and grocery requirements. But still there is a large chunk of customers who purchase from Kirana Stores.
- ☆ Majority of customer's prefer to shop for private label from Food Bazaar followed by Reliance Fresh and Food World. This shows an inclination of customer's towards known and established retail malls as compared with the new ones.
- ☆ Most of the customer's still prefer to buy basic consumption items and snack foods in private labels.
- ☆ Most of the customer's prefer private brands in comparison with the company's brands.
- ☆ Many of the customer's have high store loyalty towards private labels. However there are still a small percentage of customers who are not store loyal.
- ☆ Customers are usually store loyal but sometimes they might use the other mall
- ☆ Most of the customer's look for convenience either in terms of store location or location of the products while purchasing the grocery items
- ☆ Majority of the customers still prefer to rely on kirana stores for their day-to-day needs.
- ☆ Quality of the product plays an important role in making customers purchase from a particular retail mall
- ☆ Customer's don't seek for the offers themselves but would like to avail if they see any great offers.
- ☆ Customer's like getting a free product rather than the discounts and price refund schemes.

- ☆ Promotion is a decisive factor in the consideration set of consumer for purchasing a private label.
- ☆ Most of the consumers have the problem that they can't find all the products in private labels.
- ☆ Convenient store location is one of the important factors which consumer looks out for and they prefer to take private labels from established retail malls.

OVERALL FINDINGS

A retail store introduces its own private label for the following reasons:

- (a) **To increase customer loyalty:** The retail store wants customers to be loyal to its stores and private labels are one of the best ways to build and increase customer loyalty.
- (b) **To improve their positioning and image:** The retailers want to improve their positioning and follow a differentiated strategy, which would help them differentiate themselves from national brands and want to create a good and quality image for their stores.
- (c) **To improve margins in the category:** Usually when a retailer sells company brands he gets very less margins from the sales, usually around 10% but, when he sells his own brand his margin is around 30%.
- (d) **To lower prices to provide value for money to its customers:** Retailers generally price their brands lower than that of comparable national brands and want to provide quality products to the customers.
- (e) **To improve its bargaining power**

8. SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

- ◇ Majority of the customers visit the retail mall once in a month, thereby, retailers can bring more weekly special offers so as to bring customer more to the store. The offers should be communicated to them on time so that they can avail the benefits of it.
- ◇ There is a large chunk of customers who purchase from Kirana Store, retailers should target these customers for buying from the retail malls.
- ◇ Retailers can think of adding some more categories in the portfolio of private labels for making it more popular and to increase sales.
- ◇ Retail malls should emphasize on the quality of the product and provide better facilities to the customers.

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